

Journey Through Peritoneal Carcinomatosis: A Case Report

Modi S^{1*}, Rathod M² and Du D²

¹Jefferson Einstein Healthcare Network, Pennsylvania, USA

²Monmouth Medical Center, New Jersey, USA

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***Corresponding author:** Shivani Modi, Jefferson Einstein Healthcare Network, Pennsylvania, USA

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1. ABSTRACT

1.1. Background: Peritoneal carcinomatosis poses a diagnostic challenge due to its diverse range of differentials and late-stage presentation. This case report highlights the diagnostic journey of a 71-year-old white male with Peritoneal carcinomatosis secondary to metastatic adenocarcinoma with signet ring cell features originating from the upper gastrointestinal tract.

1.2. Case Presentation: A 71-year-old white male presented with worsening abdominal pain and discomfort over three months. Imaging revealed omental thickening, malignant ascites, and subsequent investigations led to the diagnosis of metastatic adenocarcinoma with signet ring cell features. Management complexities included pulmonary embolism, FOLFOX chemotherapy, recurrent paracentesis, and small bowel obstruction from an inguinal hernia.

1.3. Conclusion: This case underscores the importance of early detection in optimizing treatment outcomes for Peritoneal carcinomatosis. Collaboration among specialties is crucial for managing the complexities associated with this condition. Further research is needed to refine diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for advanced gastrointestinal malignancies presenting with Peritoneal carcinomatosis.

1.4. Keywords: Peritoneal carcinomatosis; Metastatic adenocarcinoma; Signet ring cell; Upper gastrointestinal tract; Abdominal pain; Malignant ascites; FOLFOX chemotherapy; pulmonary embolism

2. INTRODUCTION

Peritoneal Carcinomatosis (PC) stands as a late-stage manifestation of various gastrointestinal malignancies, creating a formidable challenge in the landscape of oncological diagnostics and management. The peritoneal cavity, a crucial anatomical space between the parietal and visceral peritoneum, becomes a battleground where malignant cells from primary tumors, most commonly originating in the colorectal, gastric, and gynaecological

regions, engage in an aggressive, infiltrative process [1,2]. Distinguishing between primary and secondary peritoneal cancers is paramount for tailoring effective therapeutic strategies.

This case report delves into the intricate diagnostic journey of a 71-year-old male with a three-month history of worsening abdominal pain and discomfort along with the subsequent diagnosis of PC, secondary to metastatic adenocarcinoma characterized by signet ring cell features within the upper Gastrointestinal (GI) tract. The urgency in addressing PC lies in its diverse differential diagnoses, ranging from infectious and inflammatory conditions to primary and secondary malignancies. The intricate interplay between these possibilities requires a meticulous evaluation to ensure an accurate diagnosis. This case underscores the critical role of early detection in optimizing treatment outcomes, shedding light on the intricate diagnostic and therapeutic challenges encountered during the hospitalization of the patient. Complications, such as aseptic fever and an acute small bowel obstruction secondary to a left inguinal hernia, highlight the need for vigilant monitoring and prompt management of unforeseen challenges in the care of PC patients.

3. CASE PRESENTATION

We present a case of 71 y/o white male with a known history of BPH treated with TURP diagnosed 5-6 years who presented to the ED with complaints of abdominal pain and discomfort which worsened over 3 months of duration. On physical examination patient had a very tense abdomen. Bowel sounds are present in all 4 quadrants.

The patient had family history of colon cancer (mother) diagnosed at 70. CT of the abdomen pelvis showed diffuse omental thickening with extensive infiltration of the omental fat by bulking soft tissue densities with omental caking. There was also abundant fluid noted in the perihepatic, peri splenic spaces and the pelvis, concerning malignant ascites. Differentials include peritoneal carcinomatosis, tuberculosis, peritonitis, and peritoneal mesothelioma. An Interventional Radiologist (IR) was consulted for paracentesis but unfortunately, could yield only 140 mL of fluid which was further sent for fluid cytology and cell count. Gastroenterology and oncology were consulted to evaluate the underlying cause and find the primary tumor (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 1: Arrow in Figures 1 and 2 suggest diffuse omental thickening with extensive infiltration of the omental fat by bulky soft tissue densities in keeping with omental caking, which can be seen with peritoneal carcinomatosis.

Hospital stay was complicated secondary to worsening of respiratory status. CT chest angiogram was obtained which showed bilateral pulmonary embolism, patient was switched to Lovenox prophylactic to therapeutic dose. Meanwhile, tumor markers including CEA was positive. Fluid cytology suggested adenocarcinoma, biopsy of the peritoneum revealed metastatic adenocarcinoma with signet ring cell features of the upper GI tract. Endoscopy revealed large partially obstructing gastroesophageal mass extending more than 5 cm in lesser curvature of the stomach. NM bone scan was obtained which was negative for osseous metastasis. Patient was initiated on chemotherapy with Leucovorin calcium, fluorouracil and oxaliplatin (FOLFOX). Patient underwent repeat paracentesis which yielded 4L fluid, providing significant relief to the patient. Hospital stay was further complicated as patient started to spike fever, was started on Zosyn empirically. Patient received antibiotics for 5 days. On day 5 blood cultures and peritoneal fluid assay was negative for infection.

Repeat paracentesis was performed again which yielded 3.2 L fluid. Eventually, tunnelled catheter was placed intraperitoneally for continuous drainage of peritoneal fluid. To combat hypoalbuminemia 25 gm albumin was started daily after placement of the catheter. Patient complained of severe abdominal pain which was followed by CT scan of the abdomen revealing acute small bowel obstruction due to left inguinal hernia and nasogastric tube was placed for decompression, which was later removed. Tumor was found to be HER2 neu negative with micro satellite instability. It was Stage 4 GE junction carcinoma with signet ring features with metastasis to peritonium. NGS shows less than 1% positive. Gross description: Consists of multiple white-tan cylindrical tissue remaining 0.1 cm - 0.9 cm × 0.1 cm × 0.1 cm. Biopsy details were noted to be: GE junction biopsy showed invasive adenocarcinoma, signet ring cell type. Immunohistochemical studies were performed with adequate controls on block A1. The tumor cells are positive for CK7 and CDX2. The morphology and immunohistochemical profile supports an upper gastrointestinal adenocarcinoma. PD-L1 Tumor proportion score less than 1%. Negative T p53. Tumor mutational burden: Not high microsatellite instability: MS-stable. HLA class I: 80*02: 01, 11: 01 space B gastric 47: 01, 40: 01 space C*03: 04, 06: 02. Negative BRAF V6 100 ED, NTRK 1/2/3 fusion, RET fusion. Negative HER2.

Patient followed for 2 cycles of FOLFOX after which he opted for comfort care and passed away.

4. DISCUSSION

The peritoneal cavity, situated between the parietal and visceral peritoneum, helps in organ mobility, fluid transport, and immune function. Peritoneal Carcinomatosis (PC) represents an advanced stage of gastrointestinal malignancies, marked by peritoneal tumor deposition [3]. Peritoneal carcinomatosis, primarily originating from colorectal, gastric, and gynaecological malignancies, poses a diagnostic challenge due to its broad differential encompassing benign conditions [4,5].

Peritoneal cancer, encompassing primary (e.g., EOPPC, mesothelioma) and secondary forms, involves malignant cells invading the abdominal cavity's serous membrane. Primary peritoneal cancer, including EOPPC, often present similarly to serous ovarian cancer, with a mean age of onset between 56-62 years and occasional association with BRCA1 mutations. Malignant peritoneal mesothelioma, linked to asbestos exposure, affects older males, while leiomyosarcoma and desmoplastic small round cells tumor have distinct associations. Secondary peritoneal carcinomatosis commonly arises from various tumors, such as those in the stomach, colon, pancreas, gall bladder, appendix, breast, uterus, ovary, and lungs, with Pseudomyxoma Peritonei (PMP) characterizing appendiceal cancer [6,7].

Primary peritoneal cancer, primarily serous carcinoma, is a rare malignancy with an age-adjusted incidence rate of 6.78 per million, most common among white individuals. Peritoneal mesothelioma constitutes 10% - 15% of mesothelioma cases, while leiomyosarcomas, often retroperitoneal, account for 50%. Peritoneal metastasis is prevalent, occurring synchronously in 55% of ovarian cancers, 5% - 10% of colorectal tumors at diagnosis, and 14% in gastric cancers, with additional dissemination from extra-abdominal malignancies in 9%, notably breast (40.8%), lung (25.6%), and melanoma (9.3%) [8,9]. The Colorectal adenocarcinomas rarely with synchronous malignancies or coexistence of other diseases like tuberculosis should be carefully looked for prognosis [10].

Common imaging features include ascites, nodular implants, and peritoneal fatty tissue infiltration, with computed tomography being the preferred modality. The Peritoneal Carcinomatosis Index (PCI) aids in assessing tumor burden, guiding decisions on cytoreductive surgery, and subsequent intraperitoneal chemotherapy, such as HIPEC or EPIC, contributing to improved life expectancy in affected patients [11]. The management and prognosis vary based on the primary cancer type and its extent of spread. Diagnosis often occurs during ascites or intestinal obstruction, indicating advanced disease with a greater tumor burden, emphasizing the importance of early detection for more effective treatment options.

5. LEARNING POINTS

- PC poses a diagnostic challenge due to its broad range of differentials, including infectious and inflammatory conditions. The complexity of PC management necessitates collaboration among various specialties, including interventional radiology, gastroenterology, and oncology.
- Complications such as pulmonary embolism and bowel obstruction may arise, requiring prompt recognition and appropriate management.
- Early detection of PC is crucial for optimizing treatment outcomes. Regular surveillance and a high index of suspicion in patients with a history of malignancy are paramount.

- Treatment strategies for PC vary based on the primary cancer type and extent of spread. Tailored approaches, including cytoreductive surgery and intraperitoneal chemotherapy, contribute to improved outcomes. Also, earlier tumor marker follow-up would be beneficial in such cases.

6. CONCLUSION

This case of a 71-year-old man with a history of benign prostatic hyperplasia and a significant family history of colon cancer highlights the complex presentation and management of advanced gastrointestinal malignancies. His presentation with worsening abdominal pain and subsequent findings of peritoneal carcinomatosis underscores the necessity for high clinical suspicion and timely diagnostic interventions in similar cases. Multidisciplinary collaboration, involving gastroenterology, oncology, and radiology, was pivotal in establishing the diagnosis and initiating appropriate treatment. Despite complications such as malignant ascites, pulmonary embolism, and small bowel obstruction, the patient received comprehensive care including chemotherapy and supportive measures like paracentesis and albumin supplementation. This case illustrates the challenges in managing advanced GI cancers and the critical role of coordinated, multi-specialty approaches in improving patient outcomes. Further research is essential to enhance diagnostic precision and develop more effective therapeutic strategies for peritoneal carcinomatosis and related malignancies.

7. DECLARATIONS

- **Ethics approval and consent to participate:** Not applicable. This case report does not involve experimental research on human subjects.
- **Consent for publication:** Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.
- **Availability of data and materials:** Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.
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- **Competing Interests:** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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